

POLITENESS OF THE ONLINE MESSAGES OF COLLEGE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Students use certain politeness strategies when communicating with teachers. However, it is concerning that some students do not seem to be aware of the politeness in sending online inquiries to teachers. To ascertain this concern, this study qualitatively analyzed the online messages of college students and determined the politeness strategies employed. The study collected nine online messages sent through Facebook Messenger and Gmail from students of a public higher education institution in Bukidnon, Philippines. The data gathered were analyzed using the Brown and Levinson Politeness Theory (1987) to find out how the online messages were categorized according to the politeness strategies used namely positive, negative, off-record and bald-on record. The politeness strategies were classified according to the students' gender and academic performance during the midterm. Upon analysis, it was found out that the college students employed various politeness strategies when writing online messages to their teacher. When classified according to gender, male college students mostly employed positive politeness strategy, female college students mostly employed positive politeness and bald-on record politeness strategy, and college students belonging to the third gender mostly employed negative politeness strategy. When classified according to academic performance, students with high academic performance mostly used positive politeness strategy, students with average academic performance mostly applied a bald-on record, and students with low academic performance mostly employed both positive and negative politeness strategy. Overall, the most common politeness strategy used by college students was positive politeness which means college students were generally polite when relaying online messages to teachers.

Keywords: *politeness, positive, negative, bald-on, off-record, college students*

INTRODUCTION

Communication between the teacher and the learner transitioned to online through text messaging, emails, Messenger app, WhatsApp, etc. However, due to that transition, concerns in the politeness of the language used arises because of the distant and non-face-to-face communication. Students employ different various politeness strategies in their social media discourse (Gervasio & Ireri, 2019). Teachers who welcome students' academic requests via SMS found that some students do not seem to be aware of the politeness in sending online inquiries. This is because traditional oral and online written communication differ in the way that information is exchanged (Ismail et al., 2023).

Politeness plays an important role in all cultures and societies for maintaining relationships (Al-Duleimi, Rashid & Abdullah, 2016). Politeness is to honor people in a polite communication (Mahmud, 2019). According to Van Olmen (2017), linguistic politeness can be defined as the ways in which language is used in conversation to show attention for the feelings and desires of a speaker, to create interpersonal relationships, and to comply with what society believes to be an appropriate behavior. A lot of theories have been proposed to examine the strategies with which politeness is expressed. The widely used theories are Brown and Levinson's (1978 & 1987), Lakoff's (1973), and Leech's (1983 & 2005) as mentioned in Al-Duleimi et al. (2016).

According to Brown and Levinson (1987), in order to save the hearers' "face", politeness strategies are developed. "Face" refers to the respect that a person has for oneself, and maintaining that "self-esteem" in public or in private situations (Ulfa, 2019). The concept of 'face' can be positive or negative. The positive face is the need to be appreciated by other people. Meanwhile, the negative face is the desire not to be concealed and to maintain their own freedom (Leontaridou, 2015). Brown and Levinson claim that there are three factors that affect the choice and use of politeness strategy, namely: power; social distance; and ranking of the imposition (Pariera, 2008). With this, politeness can be practiced according to the proximity of the individuals involved. The respect that is found in politeness can be illustrated with the nearness of the sender and the hearer including the social relationship they have (Jabur, 2019). Social distance was found to be an important factor in the actual choice of politeness strategy (AlAfnan, 2014).

A study from Manipuspika & Sudarwati (2017) and Rahmi (2020) has revealed that different politeness strategies were employed on the online messages sent by students to their lecturers and faculty through text messaging. Another study from Mulyono, et. al. (2019) also concluded the various politeness strategies employed on the messages of the students sent through WhatsApp communication. However, none of these existing studies examine the politeness strategies of messages sent through Messenger app and Google emails.

This study, therefore, demonstrated the politeness strategies employed on the online messages sent by college students through Messenger app and Google emails. The data also determined classification of politeness strategies according to the academic performance and gender of the college students.

With the results of this study, a better understanding about politeness strategies both in the discussion of theory and its applications on oral and written conversation in daily life are possible. Furthermore, an improvement on students' understanding and practice towards the method of writing online messages to their teachers is expected.

Research Questions

1. What politeness strategies do college students employ when writing online messages to teachers?
2. How do the politeness strategies on the online messages of college students differ according to their gender and academic performance?
3. What are the most common politeness strategies that college students employ when writing online messages to teachers?

METHODOLOGY

A qualitative research design was employed in the study. The researcher purposively used nine online messages from nine college students who were officially enrolled during the first semester of the school year 2021-2022. The online messages were classified according to students' gender preference, and academic performance during the midterm of the said semester. The data collected were the online messages that were asking and giving information to the teacher. The existing online messages sent through Messenger app and Google emails were analyzed using Brown and Levinson (1987) Politeness Theory. After the analysis of the online messages, the identified politeness strategies were summarized according to students' classification, and the most common strategies employed.

RESULTS

The nine online messages concerned about problems on submitting activities, asking for considerations, and informing teachers the status of their class activities. The result of this study showed that the students employed various politeness strategies of Brown and Levinson's Politeness Theory (1987).

Table 1. Politeness Strategies of Male College Students

Student	Message	Strategy
High Academic Performance	“Good morning, Sir. I just want to ask, what is the link for our Google Meet? We waited earlier at 7, Sir.” (Excerpt 1)	Positive, Negative, Off-record

Average Academic Performance	“Good evening, Sir. I have a concern about the transcreation. I cannot send my activity now because of the poor signal and sending it is my only problem. I will just send it tomorrow, Sir. Thank you for understanding and reading, Sir.”	Positive, Bald-on
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(Excerpt 2)

Low Academic Performance	“Good morning, Sir. Can I still submit for transcreation? I finished it last week but I did not turn it in. I’m hoping for your understanding.”	Positive, Negative
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(Excerpt 3)

Table 1 presents the politeness strategies (Brown and Levinson, 1987) used by the male college students as classified according to their academic performance. Almost all the politeness strategies were employed with positive politeness as the most frequently used on these online messages.

Table 2. Politeness Strategies of Female College Students

Student	Message	Strategy
High Academic Performance	“Hello Sir, good evening. I just want to inform you that I resubmitted because I have edited the video. I’m sorry Sir and I hope you understand. Thank you.”	Positive, Negative, Off-record, Bald-on
(Excerpt 4)		
Average Academic Performance	“Good evening, Sir. There are members with the same landmarks because a member had drawn again and did not notice that his drawing is similar to a groupmate, Sir.”	Positive, Off-record, Bald-on
(Excerpt 5)		
Low Academic Performance	“Good morning, Sir, I just want to say sorry that I failed to submit the activities on time Sir. I got sick last week and I am still confused as to what class I should enter. And Sir, can I ask if it is okay to enter another class section similar to this?”	Positive, Negative, Bald-on
(Excerpt 6)		

Table 2 presents the politeness strategies (Brown and Levinsons, 1987) used by the female college students as classified according to their academic performance. Almost all the politeness strategies were employed with positive politeness and bald-on as the most frequently employed strategies on these online messages.

Table 3. Politeness Strategies of Third Gender College Students

Student	Message	Strategy
High Academic Performance	<p>“Hello Sir, good evening. I would like to ask Sir what to do if our interviewee is busy? She might not have the interview because of her busy schedule Sir. Thank you very much.”</p> <p>(Excerpt 7)</p>	Positive, Negative, Off-record
Average Academic Performance	<p>“Sir, I don’t have any group because I was late during the groupings but then, I chose to be independent and I already started my activity. Also, I already have 5 interviewees.”</p> <p>(Excerpt 8)</p>	Negative, Bald-on
Low Academic Performance	<p>“Good day, Sir. We already sent our activity, Sir. I am very sorry for the confusion. We just have a misunderstanding with our groupmates.”</p> <p>(Excerpt 9)</p>	Positive, Negative, Off-record

Table 3 presents the politeness strategies (Brown & Levinson, 1987) used by the college students in the third gender as classified according to their academic performance. Almost all the politeness strategies were employed with negative politeness as the most frequently employed strategy on these online messages

Table 4. Distribution of Politeness Strategies According to Gender

Classification	Positive	Negative	Bald-on	Off-record
Male	3	2	1	1
Female	3	2	3	2
Third Gender	2	3	1	2

Table 4 presents the distribution of politeness strategies used by the students as classified according to their gender.

Table 5. Distribution of Politeness Strategies According to Academic Performance

Classification	Positive	Negative	Bald-on	Off-record
High Academic Performance	3	3	1	3
Average Academic Performance	2	1	3	1
Low Academic Performance	3	3	1	1

Table 5 presents the distribution of politeness strategies used by the students as classified according to their academic performance.

DISCUSSION

Almost all the students started with greetings when relaying online messages to their teachers (Rahmi, 2020). Greeting is a form of positive politeness where someone is giving respect to others and is aware of the sense of authority of the teacher. Eight of these nine messages used greetings and one did not. Thus, most of the students employed positive politeness on their online messages to teachers (Handayani, et al., 2023; Algiovan, 2022; Sembiring & Sianturi, 2021). Other specific uses of the politeness strategies were discussed below.

Politeness Strategies of Male College Students

For Excerpt 1, the message used a negative politeness strategy. The student used hedges in relaying his concern to the teacher (Eshghinejad & Moini, 2016). He was putting defence for himself by asking the link for their online class because they waited for the class. The message was being indirect because the real concern in the message was to inform the teacher that the student and his classmates were waiting for the class early at seven in the morning but the teacher did not show up. Instead of relaying the real concern, the student asked for the online meeting link and then informed the teacher that they waited early in the morning. The message also used an off-record politeness strategy. The student asked a question that they already knew the answer to. The student asked for the online meeting link although it was visible in their online classroom what link was to open to join the meeting. This question was relayed not just to ask but also to inform

the teacher that the student and his classmates waited early in the morning for their online meeting but the teacher did not show up.

For Excerpt 2, the message used a positive politeness strategy. The student was being optimistic on his submission of the activity. He stated that he could not submit the activity on time because of the poor internet connection, but he was confident that he could send it by the next day. This showed how confident the student was that the teacher understands him since he already thanked the understanding of the teacher despite not yet responded for consideration. Also, making a promise or an offer made this message a positive politeness strategy (Eshghinejad & Moini, 2016). The message also used a bald-on politeness strategy. The student offered to submit his activity the next day although it was past the given deadline for submission. This showed disrespect to the instructions given by the teacher. Bald-on is considered rude (Rahmi, 2020). The student was confident to submit the task the next day without hearing the consideration of the teacher towards his submission.

For Excerpt 3, the message used a negative politeness strategy. The student tried to minimize the imposition that the teacher might give after not submitting the activities on time. To do that, the student mentioned that he already finished the activity the previous week but did not submit it yet for some reasons. Although it was past the deadline for the submission and the teacher can just give no score to the student, the imposition of giving no score for the student was minimized because he mentioned that he had the activity finished and was ready for the submission already. Also, the use of questions denotes a negative politeness strategy. This was very notable from the message since the student asked the teacher if he can still submit his activity.

Politeness Strategies of Female College Students

For Excerpt 4, the message used an off-record politeness strategy. The student was trying to give hints for this message. She said that she resubmitted and edited her classwork and it did not just inform the teacher that she resubmitted but also gives a hint that the student wants the teacher to check or grade her classwork (Rahmi, 2020). The message also used an apologetic phrase, and using such phrases means negative politeness strategy (Handayani, et al., 2023). The message used a bald-on politeness strategy. The student was trying to give a warning to the teacher that she had edited her classwork just in case the teacher had already checked her output. This was a hint to recheck her submitted output worried that the teacher was not aware of her resubmission.

For Excerpt 5, the message used an off-record politeness strategy. The student was trying to give hints for this message. She said that her groupmate was not aware that he or she had drawn an artwork similar to another member. This message relayed to the teacher was not just to give information but also giving hint that the student wants the teacher to consider their output despite the mistake they made with it. The message used a bald-on politeness strategy. The student was channelling the noise that their group had experienced. She channelled the mistake done by her groupmate when he or she copied the landmark that the other groupmate had made. The student was also trying to remind

to the teacher that there was a mistake on their output. This was to make sure that the teacher was aware of their mistake in case he might wonder why the members from the group had similar drawings. This is a hint for asking reconsideration.

For Excerpt 6, the message used a negative politeness strategy. The phrase was employing an apologetic message. The student was apologizing for her failure in submitting the activities because of her poor health condition and confusion to her class schedules. Also, the use of questions employed a negative politeness strategy. The student asked the teacher if she can join other sections with the same subject. This might be because of her confusion with her class schedules. The message used a bald-on politeness strategy. The student was channelling concerns on her class schedules. She was confused on which class she should join. This was a major concern for the student which was very evident in the message particularly at the last two sentences where it talks about what class to join with. She channelled this concern to her teacher expecting advice for the confusion she had.

Politeness Strategies of College Students in the Third Gender

For Excerpt 7, the message used a negative politeness strategy. Right after greeting the teacher, the student relayed his question to the teacher. They asked for possible solutions if an interviewee was unavailable for the scheduled interview. Also, the student was being pessimistic about its message. They were thinking that the interviewee might not be available because of busy schedules. The interview was to be conducted the following week but the student already expected that the interviewee might not be available for the interview. This explains off-record politeness strategy.

For Excerpt 8, the message used a bald-on politeness strategy. The student did not greet the teacher and immediately relayed its concern and this clearly shows impoliteness. The student shows little desire to be polite to the teacher. The message also used a negative politeness strategy. The student was concerned after being late during the grouping of students for an activity. But to minimize the impositions about its condition on the activity, the student said that he already decided to work independently and already started it. This makes the teacher less worry to the student despite working alone since the student already started doing it with no other members to help.

For Excerpt 9, the message used an off-record politeness strategy. The student was trying to give a hint on the message. The student said that the activity was already sent and asked for an apology for the confusion on their submission because of the misunderstanding they had with their group. This message was not just to relay the information about their submission but it was also giving a hint that the teacher has to check their output and consider the confusion on their submission. The message also used a negative politeness strategy. The phrase indicates an apologetic message. This was because the student had problems with the submission of their output. They had a

misunderstanding with the members of the group. The student relayed this concern to the teacher and ask apology for the confusion.

Politeness Strategies According to Gender

For the male students, three of them used positive politeness strategy, two of them used negative politeness, and one male student each for bald-on record and off-record politeness. For the female students, three of them used positive politeness strategy and bald-on record, and two of them used negative politeness and off-record. For the students in the third gender, three of them used a negative politeness strategy, two of them used positive politeness and off-record, and only one used a bald-on record. With the distribution of the politeness strategies (Brown & Levinson, 1987) presented on the table, the most frequently used according to gender are: a. most of the male college students used a positive politeness strategy; b. most of the female college students used positive politeness and bald-on record and; c. most of the college students in the third sex used negative politeness strategy.

Politeness Strategies According to Academic Performance

For the students with high academic performance, three of them used positive politeness strategy, negative politeness strategy and off-record, and only one student with high academic performance used a bald-on record. For the students with average academic performance, three of them used a bald-on record, two of them used positive politeness, and one student each for negative politeness and off-record. For the students with low academic performance, three of them used positive and negative politeness strategies, and one student each for bald-on record and off-record. With the distribution of the politeness strategies (Brown & Levinson, 1987) presented on the table, the most frequently used according to academic performance are: a. Most of the college students with high academic performance used positive and negative politeness strategies; b. Most of the college students with average academic performance used a bald-on record and; c. most of the college students with low academic performance used positive and negative politeness strategy.

The distribution of politeness strategies found on the nine online messages can be classified according to academic performance and gender preference. With these classified data, the positive politeness strategy was the most dominant strategy used by the students. It was closely followed by negative politeness strategy, and equally distributed as the least used strategy are off-record and bald-on.

Conclusions

The college students employed different politeness strategies when writing online messages to their teacher. They used two or more politeness strategies on a single message they sent. When classified according to gender, male college students mostly employed positive politeness strategy, female college students mostly employed positive politeness and bald-on record politeness strategy, and college students belonging to the third gender mostly employed negative politeness strategy. When classified according to academic performance, students with high academic performance mostly used positive

politeness strategy, students with average academic performance mostly used a bald-on record, and students with low academic performance mostly used both positive and negative politeness strategy. Combining the results in all classifications of the college students, the most common politeness strategy used is positive politeness which means the participants were generally polite when relaying online messages to teachers.

Recommendations

The researcher recommends the following based from the aforementioned results:

1. Although positive politeness was the most common strategy used, there is still a portion of the students who were using bald-on strategy; thus, it is still important for teachers to teach students the proper and polite way of relaying messages to teachers;
 2. Further studies should be conducted with augmentation on the number of participants for the study. This is to ensure more valid results from varied reliable sources and participation;
 3. Further studies should be conducted with augmentation on teachers' participation. It is also important to note what the teachers has done which made students relay message, and how the teacher responded to the messages of the students online.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The students received information about the study. The researcher assured compliance with the ethical norms. The data gathered were safeguarded in order to protect the students' privacy and anonymity and to ensure the confidentiality of their messages. The researcher avoided plagiarism and shows unbiased interpretation of the findings. The results are solely for research purposes.

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